
1. The measurement of angles

ASTROMETRY IS the branch of astronomy dealing with the positions of celestial objects. Its history is a large and multiply-connected field, having its origins in the earliest records of astronomical observations more than two thousand years ago, and extending to the high accuracy observations being made from space today. Over the centuries, improved star positions led to remarkable and revolutionary advances in understanding our place in the Universe.

Perhaps foremost amongst these was the transformative understanding of the motion of the Earth, and the associated acceptance of the heliocentric hypothesis, and our understanding of the scale of the solar system. Measurements led an understanding of the motion of the Sun and Earth through space, and the comprehension and acceptance of Newtonianism. They also proved crucial to the practical task of maritime navigation.

Another challenging task which has underpinned the field for the past 400 years, and which continues to do so to this day, was that of determining distances to the stars, making use of the extended measurement baseline given by the Earth's orbit around the Sun.

When quantified for the first time in the 1830s, stellar distances revealed, at a stroke, the utter vastness of the Universe. What followed was a focus on determining the distances, motions, and physical properties of stars, and on the resulting ability to characterise the structure, dynamics – and eventually origin – of our Galaxy.

After a period in the middle years of the twentieth century in which accuracy improvements were greatly hampered by the perturbing effects of the Earth's atmosphere, ultra-high accuracies of star positions from space platforms have led to a renewed advance in this fundamental science over the past few years.

ASTROMETRY, THEN, is concerned with the accurate measurement of the positions and motions of celestial objects. This includes the positions and motions of the planets and other solar system bodies, stars within our Galaxy and, in principle, galaxies and clusters of galaxies within the Universe.

Since recording and refining the positions of the stars and planets was one of the few investigations of the heavens open to the ancients, astronomy and astrometry were largely synonymous until a little more than a century ago, when other types of astronomical investigation, such as spectroscopy, became possible.

Astrometry therefore has a remarkably long scientific history, while it remains acutely topical today. Over more than two millennia of recorded history, star positions have been measured with progressively increasing accuracy and fundamental advances in our understanding of the Universe have accompanied this progress.

As in all sciences, advances have traced out a perpetual contest between theory and observation. New ideas down the centuries demanded better observations to confirm them, while instrument advances provided new empirical evidence, stimulating new ideas. Throughout this history, advances in astrometry have benefitted from telescope improvements, from the control of measurement errors and from the ability to graduate and further subdivide angular arcs on the celestial sphere.

Recording star positions progressed through naked eye observations, later assisted by optical telescopes, through to the large-scale recording of stellar images on photographic plates of the late nineteenth century, to the high-efficiency detectors of the last twenty years.

SOME 40–50 YEARS AGO, progress ran into almost insurmountable problems imposed by the Earth's atmosphere. Scientific advances associated with improved astrometric measurements faltered, and astrometry consequently receded in global scientific importance in the face of many other rapidly-advancing branches of observational and theoretical astronomy, such as spectroscopy and cosmology. It took a back seat as observations opened up in other electromagnetic frequencies, such as in the radio, infrared, and X-ray.

But in the past two decades, unprecedented positional observations made from two satellites placed above the Earth's atmosphere have ushered in a renewed and unparalleled advance in measurement capability.

ASTROMETRIC MEASUREMENTS essentially involve determining the position of a star as it appears projected on the celestial sphere. The star's distance being, at least to a first approximation, unknown, positions at any time can be simply and uniquely specified by the two angular coordinates of spherical geometry, precisely corresponding to latitude and longitude on Earth.

The origin of the coordinate system is a delicate issue in practice, but the principle is straightforward: just as for geographical latitude, one coordinate can be tied to the extension of the Earth's equatorial plane and, as for geographical longitude and the choice of the prime meridian as its origin, the other is referenced to some arbitrary but well-defined direction in space.

The basis of astrometric measurements, then, is the accurate measurement of tiny angles that divide up the sky. Dividing a circle, whether on paper or on an imaginary sweep of the celestial sky, is a task well-posed in principle. Practical techniques for doing so aside, it is only necessary to agree on the unit of subdivision. Although scientific users today work and calculate angles in radians, the commonly accepted choice of 360 degrees in a circle was made for us long ago.

Ascribed to the Sumerians of ancient Babylonia, more than 2000 BCE, it was perhaps guided by the number of days in a year. One degree was subdivided into sixty minutes of arc, and each minute of arc was divided still further into sixty seconds of arc. The choice of sixty rests on the number itself being highly composite: it has many divisors, which facilitated calculations with fractions performed by hand.

TO VISUALISE these angles, the Sun and the Moon both cover the same *angle* on the sky, about half a degree. The much smaller one second of arc corresponds to a linear distance of one meter viewed from a distance of about two hundred kilometers. This very small angle turns out to be a particularly convenient angular measure and benchmark in astronomy, and it has been used to construct the very basic measure of astronomical distances, the parsec.

In very round numbers, one second of arc is also the angle to which astronomers can measure, with relative ease today, the position of a star at any one moment from telescopes sited below the Earth's atmosphere. It is the shimmering atmosphere which has most recently pushed these measurements to space, and a little background is useful to explain more carefully why.

The lowest portion of our atmosphere is known as the troposphere (from the Greek 'tropos' for 'turning' or 'mixing'). Extending to a height of about ten kilometers, it contains three quarters of the atmosphere's mass, and within it turbulent mixing of the air, due to convective heating rising from the Earth's surface, plays an important part in our atmosphere's structure and behaviour.

Turbulence affects light rays passing through the atmosphere, and causes the familiar twinkling of star light. Already Eratosthenes (276–194 BCE) had commented on their 'tremulous motion'. To minimise this, astronomers build their telescopes at high mountain sites where the thinner atmosphere and smaller turbulence gives more stable images. At good sites, the dancing motion might drop below a second of arc, but not by much more.

The human eye imposes its own limit to measuring angles of about one minute of arc. Mainly determined by the small diameter of the pupil through which light enters the eye, this limit is many times worse than that imposed by the atmosphere.

UNtil the invention of the telescope, observations by eye could only place far less stringent limits on the accuracy of star positions. The introduction of the telescope, credited to Dutch opticians in the opening years of the 17th century, but more famously improved upon by Galileo in 1609, brought with it two distinct improvements. First, it could detect much fainter objects, revealing vastly more than were visible by eye. The larger diameter of the telescope aperture also gave improved positional accuracies.

Making telescope mirrors larger improves the accuracy, but only up to the point that the atmospheric turbulent motion sets in at around one second of arc. Above that, even the very large 10-m class telescopes on the ground generally fail to break through the accuracy limit on angular positions set by the atmosphere.

For this reason, there is an important distinction between the angular resolution of an optical telescope, and the formal accuracy in positional location on the one hand, and the relative positional accuracies that can be achieved over large angles across the sky on the other.

SO MUCH FOR one second of arc. It is a tiny angle, corresponding to the size of a Euro coin viewed from a distance of 5 km. It remains problematic enough to measure, and one which proved a great challenge for the astronomical instrument makers of earlier centuries.

Space astrometry took a giant leap with Hipparcos in 1989, reaching accuracies of one thousandth of one second of arc. This angle corresponds to the size of an astronaut on the Moon viewed from Earth, a golf ball in New York viewed from Europe, the diameter of human hair seen from 10 km, or the (angular) growth of human hair *in one second* when viewed from a distance of 1 m.

The Gaia satellite, launched in 2013, is advancing this by a further factor one hundred, targeting accuracies of a few microseconds of arc, corresponding to one Bohr radius viewed from a distance of 1 m. Such accuracies, naturally, pose extreme engineering challenges for optical quality, detector performance, and gravitational and thermal instrumental flexure.